

Dies Natalis of Colonia Iulia Augusta Numidica Simitthensium

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Here we propose literature about the Dies Natalis of the Roman colony Iulia Augusta Numidica Simitthensium, that is Simitthus, today Chemtou, Tunisia. The Dies Natalis of the colony, founded by Augustus, was November 27.

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In Eckstein, 1979, we can find a study about the Dies Natalis of the Roman colonies. Eckstein says that the Romans traditionally commemorated a definite day of the year, celebrated as the Dies Natalis, the "birthday" of the colony (see also Sparavigna, 2020). "The question to be considered is: what action in the long sequence of actions necessary for the legal and practical founding of a colony did such a "birthday" commemorate and celebrate?" (Eckstein, 1979). Actually, the ancient Latin literature does not provide a definition of this day. We discussed in detail the different proposals about the birthday of roman towns in Sparavigna, 2022.

Eckstein tells that we know this day just in the case of four colonies. They are: "Saticula: 1 January (Festus, p. 358 Lindsay); Brundisium: 5 August (Cic. Pro Sest. 131; cf. Ad Att. 4.14); Placentia: in all probability, 31 May (Ascon. In Pis. p. 3 Clark, with Madvig's emendation; cf. now A. M. Eckstein, "Two Notes on the Chronology of the Outbreak of the Second Punic War," forthcoming in RhM); Bononia: 28 December (Livy 37.57.7)" (Eckstein, 1997).

To this short list we must add Simitthus in Tunisia and the related colony created by Augustus. We can find information in J. Linderski, "Natalis Patavii", 1983. "It is well known that not only homines and dei, but also collegia, templa and urbs had their dies natalis. First of all we have the natalis of Rome on April 21, the feast of Parilia When in 57 BC Cicero was coming home from his exile he landed on 5 August in Brundisium: *ibi mihi Tulliola mea fuit praesto natali suo ipso die, qui casu idem natalis erat et Brundisinae coloniae et tuae vicine Salutis* (Att. 4,1,4). In a later period, in 185 AD an inscription from Simitthus in Africa Proconsularis records the natalis civitatis, no doubt of Simitthus. In the fourth century we hear that Constantine celebrated the natalis of Trier, but above all we should not forget the birthday of the New Rome, the genetlia of Constantinople on 11 May. And finally an entry in the lexicon of Souda contains information about the feast of Astyromia which was celebrated para Libusin to commemorate tes poleis genetlia, presumably of Cyrene."

In Linderski's notes we can find details about Simitthus: "CIL VIII 14683 a = ILS 6824, a decree of the curia Iovis. The prescript reads as follows: *curia Iovis. acta /V k. December / Materno et [A]ttico cos. / natale civi[t]atis*. J. Schmidt, Statut einer Municipalcurie in Africa, RhM 45, 1890, 599-611, eps. 606, 610, points out that the Concilium of the curiales took place on 27 November, the anniversary of the foundation of the colonia (natale is here an abl. = natali). Simitthus was established as a colony by Augustus, see F. Vittinghoff, Römische Kolonisation und Bürgerrechtspolitik unter Caesar und Augustus, Abh. Mainz 1951, Heft 14, 112 n.2.

As it is evident, there is a colony of Augustus founded on November 27th. Some told that no colonies were founded in November, because it was an inauspicious month, that is, a month of bad omens. History says otherwise. Today, there are persons who claim to know more than Augustus did about the colonial foundation.

Fig.1: Chemtou in Google Maps

Fig.2: Map Courtesy it-ch.topographic-map.com.

In the Google Maps we can see that Simitthus had a Roman marble quarry.

An article by Philipp von Rummel and Dennis Mario Beck tells us that Simitthus/Chimtou, is the city of the "numidian marble". <https://www.dainst.blog/tana/simitthus-chimtou-2/>

“Ancient Simitthus (modern Chimtou, Tunisia) is located in northwestern Tunisia near the Algerian border. ... the city was part of the former Roman province Africa Proconsularis for over 500 years. The site is most famous for its important quarries of yellow Numidian marble. ... The site Simitthus, however, has much more to offer than the quarries and the mentioned excavated areas. As a major

Roman town, it has several temples, three public squares, baths, nymphaea, a theatre, an amphitheater, an aqueduct of 14 km length, and a labor-camp for the imperial administration, prisoners, and workmen. Furthermore, it is one of only few North African cities that witnessed a settlement ranging from the Iron Age to the Middle Ages. ... Simitthus became part of the Roman province Africa Nova in 46 BCE and was granted the status of a colony under Augustus named Colonia Iulia Augusta Numidica Simitthensium. After almost 500 years of Roman rule, the region became part of the Vandal Kingdom in 439 CE.”

In The Oxford Classical Dictionary, 2012, R. J. A. Wilson, we can find told that Chemtou is at the crossroads of the major routes from Carthage to Hippo Regius and Thabraca to Sicca Veneria. The importance of the site, however, is coming from the quarries of yellow fine marble, mentioned by Pliny too. This marble was used by Numidians who built a temple (possibly in memory of Masinissa). “Simitthus marble was first imported in Rome in 78 BC (Plin. HN. 36,49), and then on a greatly increased scale from Augustus onwards, who used it in his own forum (forum Augusti) and for the colonnade of Caesar’s forum (forum Caesaris) (Suet. Div. iul. 85). ... Augustus founded a colonia at the site, and it continued to flourish into the 3rd cent. at least; ... A unique discovery near the quarries is a 3rd cent. ergastulum for the quarry workers, converted in the 3rd cent. into a workshop for fashioning plates, basins, and statuettes of giallo antico for the export market”.

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